

Critical Entrepreneurship Skills for N.C.E Home-economics Graduates for Entry into Clothing Production Enterprise in Zamfara and Sokoto States, North-west, Nigeria

Komolafe, A. O. & Abdulrahman, M. A.

Abstract

This study identified critical entrepreneurship skills required by Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was made up of 80 respondents (60 clothing production entrepreneurs and 20 lecturers from the colleges of education in Gusau and Sokoto. The study was guided by five research objectives. Questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was face validated by five Home Economics experts. Data were analyzed using means. Findings of the study revealed all the required critical entrepreneurship skills required by Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise as ten (10) planning skills, ten (10) organizing skills, ten (10) technical skills, ten (10) marketing skills and ten (10) accounting skills. It was concluded that entrepreneurship skills in clothing production enterprise by NCE Home Economics graduates will in no doubt bring about drastic reduction in both youths and graduates unemployment and social vices. Provision of functional and adequate facilities for teaching and learning of clothing and textile production was recommended.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship skill, Clothing Production, Enterprise, Financial risks, Organizational skills

Introduction

The social and economic challenges that are currently facing Nigeria as a nation include poverty, increasing demands for improved standard of living and unemployment. This is why the Nigerian educational system is expected to rise to the challenges by equipping individuals with the requisite entrepreneurship skills required for self-reliance and job creation. The development of these skills is an important function of educational institutions, especially at the tertiary level, such as the Colleges of Education that award the Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE). Even though the current emphasis of training for the award of NCE is for teaching at the lower level, the present economic challenges of families and people have necessitated the need for

people to secure futures economically and socially.

An entrepreneur is one who organizes, manages and assumes the financial risks of a business enterprise (Okenwa, 2005). Such a person perceives business opportunities and takes advantage of the scarce resources, however, some skills are required for success in any given business enterprise. An entrepreneur is motivated by the need for achievement, independence, belief in an internal locus of control and willingness to risk business failures in order to secure success. It is expected that NCE graduates of Home Economics education should possess the required knowledge, skills and attitude that will make them to be competent in establishing an enterprise of their own.

Home Economics education program is meant to offer NCE students the opportunities of acquiring entrepreneurship skills needed for self-employment ventures. Home Economics education is a skill oriented field of study noted for its capacity of equipping learners with saleable relevant skills and knowledge that makes for self-reliance, paid employment and small business (Awo, 2012). Home Economics education graduates are expected to be prepared not only for teaching, but for adaptable employment situations of which self-employment is inclusive. One solution to unemployment is the generation of self-employment which is very possible through Home Economics entrepreneurship.

Ozioko (2006) states that entrepreneurship involves the recognition of opportunities in the form of needs, wants, problems and challenges and the use of resources to implement innovative ideas in a planned business. Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new or different with value by devoting the necessary time, assuming the accompanying financial, psychic and social risks, and receiving the resulting rewards on personal satisfaction (Onu, 2006). Skills are the means that individuals have acquired through knowledge and attitudes required in order to perform successfully at a specified proficiency level in a given work. It is a state of being functionally adequate or having sufficient knowledge, judgment, or strength in carrying out a particular job or task (Olaitan, Alaribe and Eze, 2010).

Home Economics lecturers at the NCE level are in a strategic position in equipping students with entrepreneurship skills in clothing production enterprise. The ultimate aim of education is to provide the necessary orientation for manpower and technological development of a country (Okeke, 2005). The study is

however motivated by the lack of desired knowledge and entrepreneurial skills (Planning, organizes, technical, Marketing and accounting) in clothing production enterprise. Hence, the need to determine these entrepreneurial skills in the learning of clothing production that are required to adequately equip NCE Home Economics education graduates for gainful employment self-reliance and wealth creation.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine the critical entrepreneurship skills required by N.C.E Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production in Gusau and Sokoto town of Zamfara and Sokoto States. Specifically the study identified the following entrepreneurship skills required by N.C.E Home Economics graduates for:

1. Planning clothing production enterprise.
2. Organizing clothing production enterprise
3. Mass production in clothing enterprise
4. Marketing of finished products.
5. Accounting requirements in clothing production enterprise

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. This design is adopted for social science research where data is collect from a target group seeking for their opinion, attitude and perceptions about certain phenomenon. The result of such research is generalized to a larger population group for inference.

Area of Study

This study was conducted in Gusau and Sokoto towns of Zamfara and Sokoto

States. These States have colleges of Education and Universities that offer Home Economics at the NCE level and degree levels.

Population for the Study

Population for the study was 80 respondents made up of 60 registered clothing production entrepreneurs (30 each from Gusau and Sokoto towns each) and 20 lecturers (10 each, from both Gusau FCE (T) and Shagari College of Education Sokoto).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The population of the study also formed the sample size because of the size of the whole population. Therefore, there was no sampling because of its manageable size.

Instrument for Data Collection

A four (4) point rating scale questionnaire

was developed for the various critical entrepreneurship skills in line with the specific objective of the study. The four (4) point rating scale was described and rated as: Very Critical (VC -4), Moderately Critical (MC-3), Less Critical (LC- 2) and Not Critical (NC-1). The instrument was face validated by three (3) Home Economics lecturers, FCE Zaria and Two (2) Home Economics lecturers in, Shagari College of Education, Sokoto.

Data Collection and Analysis Techniques

Eighty (80) Copies of the questionnaire were administered to sixty (60) registered clothing production entrepreneurs and twenty (20) lecturers. The 80 copies of questionnaire were completed and collected on the spot. Data were analyzed using mean. A mean rating of 2.50 and above was regarded as critical while any mean less than 2.50 was regarded as not critical.

Results and Discussions

Table1: Mean Responses of Lecturers and Clothing Production Entrepreneur on Entrepreneurship Planning Skills Required by NCE Home Economics Graduates for entry into Clothing Production Enterprise.

S/N	Entrepreneurship skills for planning clothing production	\bar{X}	Remark
1.	Set up clothing production enterprise	3.92	Critical
2.	Specify the production system to adopt and produce the plan.	4.02	Critical
3.	Knowledge of suitable location for clothing enterprise.	4.09	Critical
4.	Select appropriate equipment and tools for clothing production	3.86	Critical
5.	Identify clothing needs in the location	4.11	Critical
6.	Plan for credit facilities and other uncertainty needed for clothing production.	3.06	Critical
7.	Select qualified personnel for clothing enterprises.	3.45	Critical
8.	Identify markets for clothing products.	3.76	Critical
9.	Register the enterprise with regulatory bodies.	3.93	Critical
10.	Budget for the identified activities	3.84	Critical

N= 80 \bar{X} = Mean

Table 1: above reveals that lecturers and clothing production entrepreneurs agreed to all the ten (10) critical entrepreneurship

planning skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise.

Table 2: Mean Responses of Lecturers and Clothing Production Entrepreneurs on Entrepreneurship organizing skills required by NCE Home Economics Graduates in Clothing Production Enterprise

S/N	Entrepreneurship skills to organize clothing production	X	Remark
1.	Employ competent staff for specific jobs in clothing enterprise	3.32	Critical
2.	Provide staff with job description.	3.85	Critical
3.	Procure good materials for finishes.	3.72	Critical
4.	Acquire and arrange equipment, tools and facilities for clothing production in order to use.	4.04	Critical
5.	Provide facilities for principles of garment manufacturing.	3.50	Critical
6.	Provide general operational procedures required for clothing production.	3.73	Critical
7.	Possess adequate skills in clothing production.	3.42	Critical
8.	Provide good patterns for mass production.	4.01	Critical
9.	Purchase good fabrics and notions.	3.63	Critical
10.	Provide for maintenance and management of sewing laboratory	3.41	Critical

N= 80 \bar{X} = Mean

Table 2 above reveals that the lecturers and registered clothing production entrepreneurs agreed to all the ten (10) critical entrepreneurship organizing skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise.

Table 3: Mean Responses of Lecturers and Clothing Production Entrepreneurs on the Entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics Graduates for entry into Mass Production in Clothing Enterprise.

S/N	Entrepreneurship skills for mass production	\bar{X}	Remark
1.	A perfectly fitty garment begins with accurate measurements	4.12	Critical
2.	Know the body sizing.	3.68	Critical
3.	Acquire pattern grading technique used in producing pattern in other sizes.	3.87	Critical
4.	Standard size grading is for mass production.	3.25	Critical
5.	Individual size grading for the bespoke trade or custom made.	4.02	Critical
6.	Place emphasis on operation specialization.	3.04	Critical
7.	Make use of operation engineering.	3.46	Critical
8.	Workers stick to areas of specialization.	4.03	Critical
9.	Workers are faced with daily insecurity as their employment is determined by fashion trends and market fluctuations.	3.88	Critical
10.	There are division of labour in mass production	3.65	Critical

N= 80 \bar{X} = Mean

Table 3: Table 1: above reveals that the lecturers and registered clothing production entrepreneurs agreed to all the ten (10) critical entrepreneurship planning skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise.

Table 4: Mean Responses of Lecturers and Clothing Production entrepreneur on Entrepreneurship Skills required by NCE Home Economics Graduates for Marketing Finished Clothing Products

<u>S/N Mass Clothing Products Entrepreneurship skills required for Marketing Finished</u>	<u>\bar{X}</u>	<u>Remark</u>
1. Analysis of what customers are actually buying.	3.42	Critical
2. Identify marketing demands for styles, colours, fabrics etc that are in high demand.	3.23	Critical
3. A new strategy known as data mining is being used to go far beyond analyzing point-of-sale data to help producer.	4.04	Critical
4. Because trimming in fashion is of utmost importance, there is no real place for wholesale, middlemen in the marketing of fashion goods.	3.06	Critical
5. Vary the method of introducing new fashions to buyers.	3.21	Critical
6. Maintain sales staff showrooms.	3.03	Critical
7. Use independent setting representative that maintains permanent showrooms.	3.76	Critical
8. Advertise in social media and use modern technology to improve marketing	3.07	Critical
9. Remember customers are always right in the marketing ethics.	3.28	Critical
10. Consider more of fashion classic than fad and status symbol.	3.24	Critical

N = 80 \bar{X} = Mean

Table 4 above reveals that the lecturers and registered clothing production entrepreneurs agreed to all the ten (10) critical entrepreneurship planning skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise.

Table 5: Mean Responses of Lecturers and Clothing Production Entrepreneurs on the Entrepreneurship Financial Management Skills Required by NCE Home Economics Graduates for entry into Clothing Production Enterprise

<u>S/N Financial Management Skills required for Clothing Production Enterprise</u>	<u>\bar{X}</u>	<u>Remark</u>
1. Prepare financial statements for mass clothing	3.78	Critical
2. Determine source of funds for mass clothing production	4.02	Critical
3. Obtain loans for mass clothing production	3.68	Critical
4. Pay government levies, taxes and regulations for clothing production	3.47	Critical
5. Determine what to purchase to fit into the budget for mass clothing production	3.82	Critical
6. Prepare cost analysis in clothing production	3.45	Critical
7. Prepare a simple budget for clothing production	3.94	Critical
8. Procure appropriate consumable-materials for clothing production	4.08	Critical
9. Make purchasing needs record/compare for clothing production	4.11	Critical
10. Keep purchase records for clothing production	3.92	Critical

N=80 \bar{X} = mean

Table 5above reveals that the lecturers and registered clothing production entrepreneurs agreed to all the ten (10) critical entrepreneurship planning skills required by NCE Home eEconomics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise. The ten (10) required entrepreneurship skills had their mean value range from 3.45 to 4.08 items number 6 and 9 respectively which was above 2.50 mean rating.

Discussion

Table 1 of the Study identified, ten (10)

critical entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Homes, economics graduates in Gusau and Sokoto towns for planning clothing production enterprise the ten (10) items were considered significantly critical by the respondents. The result indicates that knowledge and identification of suitable location for clothing enterprise and clothing needs of the marketing audience of the location had the highest mean of 4.11. This is in agreement with Ohwovoriole & Ochonogor (2008) who asserted that knowledge is required by students for performance in any field of endeavor. The study implies that entrepreneurship is the ability to seek investment opportunities based on identified opportunities. The study affirms the assertion of Olaitan et. al. (2010) that exposure to a variety of knowledge and skills are facilitated through experiences that are meaningful.

Table 2 identified ten (10) critical entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for organizing clothing production enterprise. The study revealed the entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates include; employing competent staff, providing staff with job description, procurement of good materials, acquiring and arranging materials, operational procedures, possessing and purchasing tools and equipment, maintenance and mass clothing production. The study is in tandem with Olaitan & Mama (2001) who asserted that drawing up a business program plan procurement of facilities including raw materials, are vital skills for successful business enterprise. Onu (2006) sees an entrepreneur as one who chooses or identifies business opportunities, gathers resources, initiates action and establishes an organization or enterprise to meet such demand or market opportunity.

Table 3 of the study identified ten (10) critical entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into mass clothing production enterprise. Kitty in Emelue (2010), explained that there are some skills needed for mass production. Ten (10) critical entrepreneurship skills were identified as required by NCE Home Economics graduates for marketing finished clothing products of which all were considered significantly critical. The study revealed these marketing skills as; analysis of marketing opportunities, identify marketing demands for styles, colours of fabrics in high demand, new strategy, importance of trimming, new fashions show room and records, maintaining sales staff, sales representatives, and advertisement in social media. This is in line with the study of Obiyai & Ekubo (2011) who asserted that skills in marketing include: advertised products, identify customers to patronize, maintain good customer relationship; identify business opportunities and market channels.

Table 5 of the study identified ten (10) critical entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for financial management in clothing production enterprise. The study revealed the entrepreneurship financial management skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates for entry into clothing production enterprise to include: Preparation of financial statements, determination of sources of funds, loans, purchases in the budget, payment of government levies, taxes, preparation of cost analysis, preparation of simple budget, facilities procurement of consumable materials, purchases and record keeping. The study is in consonance with Awo, & Ukonze (2012) who stated that book-keeping records and basic accounting practices are the

foundation of whole and balanced accounting framework which indicates effective financial operations. In line with this study Igbo in Shobowale (2014) observed that entrepreneurs should be able to interpret financial statement, prepare financial statement, and understand payroll and various deductions, know gross and net profit, know sources of funds, pay government levies, taxes and regulations, acknowledge factors involved in decision to grant loan by financial institutions.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study has identified entrepreneurship skills required by NCE Home Economics graduates in clothing production enterprise for their economic independence, self-reliance and wealth creation. Entrepreneurship skills in clothing production enterprise by NCE Home Economics graduates will in no doubt bring about drastic reduction in both youths and graduates unemployment and social vices.

Based on the findings of study, the following recommendations were made;

1. There is need for the review of Home Economics curriculum to accommodate Book-keeping records and Business Management as core curricula matter in consumer Education, which is presently being taught at this level. This will enhance financial management of Home Economics business enterprises.
2. Field trips and Students Industrial Working Experience Scheme are quite relevant to equipping Home economics students with entrepreneurship skills in clothing production enterprise. These institutions should be listed as one of the sites for students SIWES.

References

- Ajala, E.O. and Olaitan, S.O, (2010) Provision and utilization of facilities for enhancement of Learning experiences of nursery school children. *Nigerian Vocational Journal*. 14 (2) 83-91
- Awo, O.K and Ukonze, J. A. (2012) Technical and Entrepreneurial Competences Needed by NCE Home economics students for self-reliance in youths production enterprises. *Journal of Home Economics Research*. 17,138-148
- Emelue, F. (2010) Selected Entrepreneurship Skills required by yoghurts in clothing production. *Journal of Home Economics Research*. 209-215
- Obiyai, K.K. and Ekubo, N.A. (2011) Development of Entrepreneurship skills training module on fish breeding and hatching occupation. *Asian journal of Agricultural science*. 3 (2), 111-114. Retrived match 19th, 2019, <http://www.maxwellsci.com/print/ajas/v3pdf>.
- Ohwovewole, P.I. and Ochonogor, E.O. (2008) Equipping NCE Home economics with life skills for entrepreneurship development. *Journal of Home Economics Research*. 9,254-261.
- Okeke, C.A. (2005) Improving students' skill acquisition through effective clothing and textile education in tertiary institutions in Anambra state. *Journal of Home Economics Research*. 6 (1) 84-89
- Okenwa, C.P (2005) *Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria: A practical Approach*. Enugu: Snaap press (Nig) Ltd.
- Olaitan, S.O; Alaribe, M.O. and Eze, S.O. (2010) Competency Improvement needs of teachers in secondary schools in Abia state. *Nigerian Vocational Association Journal*. 15 (1) 335-341.
- Onu, W.C. (2006) Practical tips to successful entrepreneurship in Anyakola, E.U

- (Ed) *Practical Tips for Economic Empowerment and survival*. HERAN
- Ozioko, J.N.C (2006) Promoting Entrepreneurship through Developing Creativity. *Journal of Home Economics Research* 7 (Special edition) 164-170.
- Shobowale, I.O. (2014) Entrepreneurship skills required by Technical College Graduates for Entry into Upholstery and Furniture-Making Enterprise in Lagos state. *Journal of Home Economics Research*.